

SPECIFIC AREAS OF THE NAVOI REGION IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM**Ramatov Murat Kalvayevich**

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Annotation. *This article reveals the concept of historical-cultural tourism, its role in the field of Tourism. Opportunities and prospects for the development of historical and cultural tourism are analyzed.*

Keywords: *tourism, historical-cultural tourism, historical monument, statistics, cultural heritage, tourist product, restoration.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрено понятие историко-культурного туризма, его особенности в сфере туризма. Проанализированы возможности и перспективы развития историко-культурного туризма.*

Ключевые слова: *туризм, историко-культурный туризм, исторический памятник, статистика, культурное наследие, туристский продукт, реставрация.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tarixiy-madaniy turizm tushunchasi, uning turizm sohasidagi o'рни o'ziga xos jihatlari ochib berilgan. Tarixiy-madaniy turizmni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari va istiqbollari tahlil qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *turizm, tarixiy-madaniy turizm, tarixiy yodgorlik, statistika, madaniy meros, turistik mahsulot, qayta tiklash.*

The tourism industry is one of the leading sectors of world economy and is a promising sector that brings high income to the national economy. Tourism accounts for about 5% of the world's GDP, with nearly 10% of the population in developed countries employed in tourism.

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the tourism sector is one of the largest hit sectors. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), in 2020, international tourism fell by 72% or revenues from tourism services by \$ 1.1 trillion, falling to the level of 1990. 935 crore as a result. export earnings in the amount of dollars were lost . As you know, from March 16, 2020, our country was closed to foreign and domestic tourists. As a result, more than 1.5 thousand tour operators, 1.2 thousand hotels ceased their operations. These, combined with guides, National Crafts, shrines and shrines, catering, transportation, etc, seriously affected the income of more than 250,000 residents. There are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage in Uzbekistan,

such as historical monuments, monuments built with the highest talent of our great ancestors, holy steps, and most of them are listed on the UNESCO list. Therefore, in the following years, many regulatory legal acts on the development of this direction are being adopted by our state. In particular, according to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2021 “on measures to further improve the system of Public Administration in the fields of Tourism, Sports and cultural heritage” PF-6199, a cultural heritage agency was established under the Ministry of Tourism and sports. It is important to carry out systematic scientific and methodological research on the further development of historical and cultural tourism in our country, such as the identification, accounting, protection, promotion of objects of material cultural heritage as the main tasks of the agency, such as the state register, electronic catalog, maintaining the state cadastre, marking protected tegras, as well as state control in the field. Historical monuments in Uzbekistan, monuments built with the high talent of our great ancestors, there are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage, such as the Holy steps, and most of them are on the UNESCO list. Therefore, in the following years, many regulatory legal acts on the development of this direction are being adopted by our state. In particular, according to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2021 “on measures to further improve the system of Public Administration in the fields of Tourism, Sports and cultural heritage” PF-6199, a cultural heritage agency was established under the Ministry of Tourism and sports. It is important to carry out systematic scientific and methodological research on the further development of historical and cultural tourism in our country, such as the identification, accounting, protection, promotion of objects of material cultural heritage as the main tasks of the agency, such as the state register, electronic catalog, maintaining the state cadastre, marking protected tegras, as well as state control in the field. Thus, it is relevant to analyze the current state of historical and cultural tourism, the prospects for its development and its impact on the national economy. First of all, it is necessary to determine the content of the concept of “historical-cultural tourism”. Review of thematic literature .

It should be noted that in the context of the current pandemic, there is no single concept among many authors regarding the preservation of the sectors that make up the tourism infrastructure from the crisis. In our opinion, the scope of research that still needs to be carried out in this regard is wide, and we must also take into account international experiences in ensuring the development of Tourism networks. In the economic literature, issues related to historical-cultural tourism have been studied by a number of scholars and given different

definitions. Dutch researcher Richard Greg describes historical-cultural tourism as “the way people go to cultural, attractions far from their usual place of residence with the aim of gathering new information and experience to meet their cultural needs.” Russian specialist Y.V. Kolotova defines historical-cultural tourism as “the potential of the socio-cultural environment, connected by traditions and Customs, the peculiarities of the household, which include all the possibilities of the country.” I.T. Frolova, on the other hand, looks at historical cultural tourism as a factor and tool that brings peoples closer together on a global scale, three whose development is interconnected and complementary:

- 1) enrichment of knowledge about culture and cultural heritage,
- 2) protection and restoration of culture,
- 3) from such directions as the dialogue of cultures

believes to consist. In other words, currently the main humanitarian functions of cultural tourism, as the following are noted:

- cultural-educational and educational; - cultural protection and preservation;

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G.Karpov. L.The khorovas, on the other hand, insist that historical and cultural tourism is “a visit by local residents to traditional recreation areas, innovative art houses, reflecting cultural attractions, museums and historical places, art galleries, music and drama theaters, concert venues, performing arts, classical values and historical heritage” in order to gain new information, experience and impressions. Political and legal factors of our country:

- Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on tourism”, decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to further improve the system of Public Administration in the fields of Tourism, Sports and cultural heritage”, decree of the Cabinet of

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Bukhara, Samarkand, Resolution No. 939” on measures to ensure safe tourism in the cities of Khiva and Shahrisabz.) Other industry-specific decrees are presidential and government decisions (including easing the issuance of licenses and permits;

- Ensuring political stability in the country;

- The presence of specific mechanisms and programs for the restoration, preservation and protection of historical archaeological monuments and cultural works of art in our country; - the establishment of a visa-free entry regime for tourists from 90 countries; - ensuring stable peace in the country and low crime rates; - the focus of Uzbekistan's foreign policy on promoting transparency and developing regional and multilateral interaction;

- Introduction of a new mechanism for systematic work on improving the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international rankings and indices; - formation of mechanisms of openness, transparency and accountability in public administration;

- The introduction of the concept and standards of “safe tourism” in Uzbekistan from 2017; - the ban on free travel of tourists as a result of the closure of borders in the context of a pandemic.

Conclusions and suggestions

When researching the possibilities of effective use of historical and cultural tourism sites, it is necessary to identify ways to increase their effective use, the factors affecting them and their identification, as well as to group resources to assess the possibilities of using tourist resources, as well as identify indicative indicators of their conservation, restoration activities.

As a result of the theoretical and practical study of improving the economic efficiency of the industry, the following conclusions were drawn and recommendations were developed: - improving the quality and exemplary service of museums and cultural heritage objects and strengthening their reputation through this; - organizing cultural events such as an International Exhibition, Conference, festival in the demonstration of the country's historical heritage in the world; - by significantly increasing the role of archaeological monuments in the field of historical cultural tourism, bringing them to the level of the brand among foreign and domestic tourists; - preparing archaeological monuments for a museum exhibition in part (conservation and restoration); - to introduce the traditions of national crafts to the world with the establishment of master classes in folk centers of Applied Arts for tourists.

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